

The publishing process

As a peer-reviewed journal article

As a preprint

Proof of productivity

Many funders accept preprints in grant applications. Preprints receive a DOI** and can be cited.

Wide visibility

Preprints are available via search tools such as Google Scholar or Europe PMC.

Journal compatible

Most journals in the life sciences accept preprints.

Scoop protection

Many journals operate scoop protection policies starting from the date of the posted preprint.

Find more information at ASAPbio.org

* Might be behind a paywall

** arXiv uses its own system of persistent identifiers for preprints